

THE ROLE OF PROFESSIONAL REFLECTION IN THE PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY OF A PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article describes how to improve the organization and management of reflective thinking among elementary school teachers, analyzing information and prioritizing substantive relationships in joint actions*

Keywords: *UNESCO, critical thinking, literacy and numeracy, reflexive activity, pedagogical experiences*

In the world, education appears as the main factor that ensures the development of a person. In the international concept of education set by UNESCO until 2030, "quality education stimulates creative thinking and knowledge, develops the fundamentals of literacy and numeracy, as well as analytical, problem-solving, reasoning and other interpersonal and social skills at a high-level guarantee possession" [1], it is noted. This determines the development of reflexive skills such as creative thinking, critical thinking, self-evaluation, understanding of historical reality, and analysis of one's own activities among students in the general secondary education system. The analysis of pedagogical experiences at the international level shows that the development of strategies for improving the processes of formation of reflexive skills in students and the design of mechanisms for its implementation are of great importance in ensuring the effectiveness of education.

In the processes of formation of reflexive skills in teachers of general secondary educational institutions, the teacher thinks more analytically about himself and independently assimilates the new concepts being studied, that is, it takes place in independent thought processes when the teacher is not traditionally taught by the student.

Encouraging primary school teachers to self-analysis, objective assessment of their understanding, activity and activity, i.e., reflexive activity, to study history, the conditions of the period before the independence of our country and creates situations encouraging to study, analyze and objectively assess the historical way of life of our ancestors. Therefore, in order to form reflexive skills in teachers, it is important to consider the following processes as directions of their reflexive activity:

1. Self-analysis and objective evaluation: analysis of one's own concepts and ideas; comparing their understanding, imagination and behavior with the understanding, imagination and behavior of their peers and siblings; objective assessment of one's behavior; analyze how one is perceived by peers, comrades and other people; understanding and self-control with whom one interacts in the process of communication.

2. Comparison, analysis, objective evaluation and conclusion of the past (history) with the present: study of the relationship between the past and the present in relation to the studied concepts; their comparison, analysis and objective assessment; formation of objective ideas about independence, its essence, importance and necessity; formation and development of reflexive activity skills.

In order to form a conscious discipline instead of forced obedience in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in elementary school teachers, it is necessary to take into account the following features specific to these processes: the teacher's activity with students is a unique integrative system; interdependence of students' inclinations, personal capabilities, initial concepts and personal interests;

Disproportion of effectiveness in the processes of formation and development of reflexive skills in teachers (paying special attention or not paying attention to the active student or group of students); the need to create a reflexive educational environment in educational institutions; that the processes of educational relations are of practical importance.

The process of forming reflexive skills in students is a complex pedagogical system that covers a wide range of features specific to the system. In turn, socio-psychological functions are performed by teachers in the process of effective performance of their functional tasks in this system.

Ensuring the effectiveness of the processes of forming reflexive skills in teachers in all aspects of planning, organization, motivation and control processes by managers, specialists and teachers, information analysis, goal-motivation, foresight-planning, organizational-executive, effective implementation of control-diagnosis, regulation-coordination functions is envisaged. The essence and importance of the implementation of these functions is expressed in the following processes: planning processes of formation and development of reflexive skills; ensuring the activity of teachers and forming their interest in learning; aligning the set goals and available opportunities with the interests and needs of students; to stimulate students' level of basic concepts, abilities, personal characteristics, interests, as well as reflexive activity based on coordination, control, analysis and objective evaluation according to situations.

The second pedagogical condition for the development of pedagogical reflection is the existence of a reflexive environment. Reflexive environment is a specific system of personal development conditions that open up the possibility of self-research of socio-psychological and professional resources and self-correction. The function of this type of environment is to create the basis for the need for reflection in the individual. A.A. Bizyayeva spoke about the "reflexive-innovative environment", where co-creation is encouraged, conditions for selection are created, as a result of which a change occurs in the perception of oneself as a person and a professional. The goal of creating a reflexive environment is to prevent the pedagogue from moving away from the educational process and to develop professional reflexivity as a way of life (professional activity). Working with the thoughts and values of the pedagogue on the existential phenomenon, individual activity as the main directions of working in a reflexive environment; carrying out a psychologically safe (non-evaluation) diagnosis of professional qualities and using the obtained results to improve professional skills; the development of the creative uniqueness of the pedagogue is manifested.

The third pedagogical condition for the development of pedagogical reflection is the activation of intersubjective relations between the participants of reflexive activity. In the conditions of reflexive activity, the specific characteristics of the relationship in the pedagogical process require the participation of both the teacher and the learner as subjects of activity, in which their common activity takes place synchronously, and each of them preserves the uniqueness of their behavior. complement and enrich each other's activities. It is precisely in such mutual

transitions from subject-object relations to subject-subject relations that the mechanisms of professional reflection of the pedagogue are embodied.

The pedagogical process is organized and implemented by the teacher in order to create suitable conditions for the development of students. This means that all elements of reflection in the pedagogical process are related to reflections in the student's activity. This situation makes it necessary that the reflections on the future teacher's activity and the reflections of interaction are always proportional to the goal.

REFERENCES

1. Incheon Declaration/Education 2030: Towards inclusive and equitable quality education and lifelong learning for all (World Education Forum, May 19-22, 2015, Incheon, Republic of Korea).
2. Khakimova DM Didactic features of formation of reflexive skills in students. //Teacher and continuous education. – Nukus, 2018.-№3. - В. 21-22. (13.00.00 2018)
3. Метаева В.А. Рефлексия и её рол в преодолении профессиональных затруднений педагога: Дис. канд. пед. наук – Екатеринбург, 2016.- 207 с.
4. Семёнов И.Н. Развитие рефлексивно-критического мышления как компонента экзистенциально-ориентированного образования //Духовност и рефлексивност в становлении профессионала: Материали межд.науч-практ. семинара: – М.: 1997.- С.27-32.